

Study Various Methods and Use Wavelet Transform for Fault Detection and Classification of Underground Transmission Line by Using MATLAB

Author's Details: Md. Zamilis Siam¹, Diponkar Kundu²

¹Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Pabna University of Science and Technology, Pabna 6600, Bangladesh, Email: zamilis.pust.20@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Pabna University of Science and Technology, Pabna 6600, Bangladesh, Email: d.kundu.eee@gmail.com

Abstract:

Underground cables are being faced with a wide variety of faults due to underground conditions, wear and tear, etc. Diagnosing fault source is difficult and the entire cable should be taken out from the ground to check and fix faults. This paper presents the details of faults and the Wavelet transform-based technique for fault detection, classification in the Underground transmission line. Due to the fault in the power system, a high-frequency current and voltage generate and propagate along with the power. These generated signals contain a lot of information and can be used for fault detection and location. The high-frequency components generated are extracted using the wavelet technique and analysis of the extracted signals is carried. The MATLAB Simulink is used to model the underground cable network and faults at various locations are simulated. The resulting waveforms are subjected through a wavelet transform to extract the required signals for analysis. The presented model is user friendly and can be used as a common platform for both control and power system engineers. The accuracy of the wavelet transform scheme is 100%.

Keyword: Fault, Wavelet Transform, SIMULINK, MATLAB, Underground, Transmission.

I. Introduction

The economic growth and development of a country depend greatly on the reliability and quality of the electric power supply [1]. Overhead transmission lines are being used in the current power system which is not much reliable or safe so to overcome its problem and developed a smart city underground cables are used [2]. Underground cable installations are costly as compared to overhead cables, but underground cables are more preferable since underground cables are not affected by a climatic

condition like earthquakes, lightning, heavy rain, winds, snowfall, etc.[1-3][4]

In the underground system, it is quite difficult to find the faulty area than the overhead system because of a few obvious reasons the entire cable should be taken out from the ground to check and fix faults. There are so many techniques in an overhead system

like the Phasor Measurement Unit which is capable of identifying the accurate location of the fault and its types. But in the case of underground systems, such systems cannot be used.[5] So this paper core objective is detect the underground fault with 100% accuracy by using Wavelet Transform.

a. Fault location method can be classified as

Online method utilize process the sampled voltage & current to determine the fault points. Online method for underground cable is less than overhead line [6, 7]. Example: Artificial Neural Network, Continuous/complex wavelet transform

Offline method special instrument is used to test out service of cable in the field there are two offline methods as following: [6, 7].

In tracer method fault point is detected by walking on the cable line. Fault point is indicated from audio able signal or electromagnetic signal. It is used to pinpoint fault location very accurately [7]. Example: Tracing current method, Sheath coil method.

Terminal method is technique to detect fault location of cable from one or both ends without tracing. This method use to locate general area of fault expedite tracing on buried cable. Example: Murray loop method, Impulse current method [7].

b. fault in a cable can be classified into different types such as

Open circuit faults are better than short circuit fault because when this fault occurs current flows through cable become zero. Open circuit fault is a kind of fault that occurs as a result of the conductor breaking or the conductor being pulled out of its joint sometimes faults occur when one or more phase conductors break [1-4, 7].

Short Circuit Fault when two or more conductor of the same cable in contact with each other, then this is called a short circuit fault. It is impossible to detect visually without taking the cable apart. A short circuit fault occurs when the individual insulation of the cables is damaged [1-4, 7].

Short circuit fault can be categorized in two types

Symmetrical fault Three-phase fault is called symmetrical fault. In this all three phases are short circuited [2, 7].

Unsymmetrical fault In this fault magnitude of current is not equal & not displaced by 120 degree [2, 7].

II. Literature Review

A literature survey is necessary to complete a journal/paper because it describes the previous works about the working topic and analysis thoroughly this analysis supply the researcher with necessary information about the methodologies and technologies available on that working topic.

In [5], Mr. M. R. Hans, Ms. Snehal C. Kor, Ms. A. S. Patil uses the simple concept of OHMs law for building the prototype. The current would vary depending upon the length of fault of the cable determined the underground fault by using a terminal method with prototype Murray loop method it identifies the fault accurately but the method is a costly and is a slow method. In this paper, fault detects in a short transmission line but in my paper, underground problems are detected in long-distance transmission lines. And also the proposed model and fault detection technique is friendly that any operator or engineer can be handled easily.

In [1], the author determined the underground fault by using a MATLAB SIMULATION and detected

the underground fault but the main problem is the model used in this paper is so complex and costlier. But in this paper a simple model is provided and any operator can easily maintain.

In [7] Kajal Bagade, Gita Bhardwaj, Shweta Wasnik, Dheeraj Kawade, Payal Mool, Rupali Mohatkar provided a prototype block diagram and detected the underground fault accurately with the help of IOT (internet of Things). but our country does not have enough internet speed and if there is any interrupt in providing internet then the model or technique is not accepted. On the other side wavelet based underground fault detection does not have this type of problem.

In [8], the author used Complex Wavelet Transform for identifying the underground fault not that accurately then Wavelet Transform in wavelet transform the mother signal by discrete filter bank and extract the feature then complex Wavelet Transform.

In [9], Abhishek Pandey, Nicolas H. Younan detected the underground fault by fourier transform. Wavelet transform method offers important advantages over other methods such as FT due to good time and frequency localization characteristics. Analysis results presented clearly show that particular wavelet components can be used as the features to locate the fault in underground cables in distribution system.

In [10], T Cable faults are damaged to cables which affects the resistance in the cable. If allowed to persist, this can lead to a voltage breakdown. To locate a fault in the cable, the cable must first be tested for faults.

III. Theory

When a mathematical function represented by wavelets it is a wavelet transform [11]. Wavelet transform is similar to Fourier transforms, but it has a difference it assumes time localization of various frequency components of a particular signal. For detecting precisely it can analyze a signal into high-frequency components and low-frequency components. Sometimes Windowed Fourier transforms also showing this type of advantage but it has a limitation. Because of using a fixed wide windowing function [12]. Wavelet transforms also show a property called multi-resolution in which

higher frequency wavelet narrow and lower frequency broader, By using this property transients fault can be analyzed which contains high-frequency components in power signals. Because of having these advantages by using wavelet transform underground transient fault can be identified easily. There are two types of Wavelet transform (1) Discrete wavelet transform (2) Continuous wavelet transform

Continuous wavelet transform define as a

$$CWT(a,b; f(t), \Psi(t)) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} \Psi\left(\frac{t-b}{a}\right) dt$$

Where a is the scaling parameter, b is the time parameter, $f(t)$ is the signal which is transformed, $\Psi(t)$ is the mother wavelet [12]

By using Continuous wavelet transform we can transform the inner outcome of a signal. By rewriting the CWT equation into frequency-based signal we can get inverse Fourier transform.[12]

$$CWT(a,b; f(t), \Psi(t)) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \hat{f}(\omega) \sqrt{a} \hat{\Psi}(\omega) (a\omega) e^{jab} d\omega$$

Where $f(t), \Psi(t)$ is the signal and the wavelet for Fourier transform. Curving the center frequency for the wavelet shifts towards lower frequencies CWT equation act as a bandpass filtering for the input signal. This property can be used for feature extracting from output signal analyze.

Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT), where the scale and translation are discredited, but not are independent variables of the original signal.

$$DWT(m,n) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2^m}} \int_k^0 f(k) \Psi\left(\frac{n-k2^m}{2^m}\right)$$

Where $\left(\frac{n-k2^m}{2^m}\right)$ is the mother wavelet[11].

IV. Proposed Model

Figure 1: Proposed system for Detecting fault analysis

The proposed test system consisting of a three-phase source which generates the power at 50 Hz and 11 kV, a two winding transformer, a 250km long transmission line, V-I measurement, and a three-phase series R-L-C load has been provided in Fig. 1. The three-phase resistive-inductive-Capacitive (RLC) the load is considered in this study. The transmission line has been considered in two parts first side having a length of 200km and the second side having 50 km. These two parts are designated as TRL-1 and TRL-2. The fault under investigation has occurred close to the second side of the transmission line i.e. at a distance of 50 km from the load. The voltages illustrated in the simulation results are measured on the V-I measurement on the load terminal (Bus B-2).

V. Proposed Cable Configuration

Figure 2: Cable Configuration

VI. Parameters of the Proposed Model

Table 1: Parameter

Object	Parameter
Three phase Source	VL=11kV, f=50Hz, Xs:Rs=10, Xs=2Ω, Rs=20Ω
Cables	XLPE, Three-phase cable
Distribution parameter cable1,2	Length =100m, f=50Hz
Transformer: Winding 1	S=1 MVA VL=11kV, Rp=1 Ω, Lp=28.6mH
Transformer: Winding 2	S=1 MVA VL =380V, Rs=0.00044 Ω, Ls=0.0114mH
Three-phase static Load	VL=380 Vrms, f=50 Hz, PL=92.62kW, QL=69.252 kVAR

VII. Methodology

Fault classification and location identifies means which type of fault occurs in the transmission line and where it occurs. At this point for classifying the occurring fault, we used a wavelet-based multiresolution analysis which is basically a special property of discrete wavelet transform. It is a feature extracting technique in which the multiresolution model is constructed by a filter which is called a quadrature mirror filter, which means it contains two filters a low pass filter and a high pass filter, and both filters relate each other. The resultant output signal from the HP filter is known as detailed coefficients, and from the LP filter are known as

approximated coefficients. First, the input signal passing through a low pass filter and high pass filter with impulse response and completes the first level. For classifying the identified fault we need detail coefficients because of this decomposition is repeated to further increase the frequency resolution and the approximation coefficients decomposed with high and low pass filters and then down-sampled. This is represented as a binary tree with nodes representing a sub-space with a different time-frequency localization. The tree is known as a filter bank.

Figure 3: Filter Bank

a. Feature Selecting

Proper fault detection and classification technique is depend on selecting the correct feature selection. After decomposing the mother signal by discrete filter bank taking the required feature. In filter bank the mother signal decomposed in 3rd level. In this technique those proper of a signal are selected which have high frequency.

b. Fault classifying by current coefficient

For identification of fault, phase currents I_{as} , I_{bs} , I_{cs} are gained from the transmission end of the transmission line. Then mother signals are decomposed by DWT filter bank. The ground signal I_g is calculated. Fault is identified on a individual transmission line if and only if the count of utmost value of the detail coefficients of the transmission line currents is higher than threshold limit. After the fault has been identified, it is easy whether it is occurred.

The ground current is calculated

$$I_g = I_{as} + I_{bs} + I_{cs}$$

Figure 4: Block diagram of fault classification technique by current

c. Fault classifying by voltage coefficient

After identifying the grounded and ungrounded faults. The other faults need to be classified. For these reasons, the voltage of the first detailed coefficients are calculated in standard deviation corresponding to the energy in each phase I.e. V_a , V_b , and V_c .

Figure 5: Block diagram of fault classification technique by voltage

After completing the fault classification, the next step is to determine the location of the fault. The location of fault means where the fault occurs in the power system. Because of a fault occurring in the system, a high-frequency voltage and current suddenly propagate along with the power. The traveling wave theory method uses the information got from the faulty place of voltage and current traveling waves for locating the fault. The first peak time obtained from the faulty bus is employed for calculating the distance of fault from the sending end. This technique is mostly used for extra high voltage transmission lines than distribution lines because the distribution system contains many subsections such as laterals and feeders. It includes two methods – the single-ended method and the double-ended

VIII. Simulation Result and Discussion

The simulation is carried out for 14-16 cycles. In each case study, the fault is created in the 4th cycle. The current is measured at the load terminal in each case study. The rated voltage is 11 kV and the same voltage level is considered at all points of the system. The first peak time obtained from the faulty bus is employed for calculating the distance of fault from the sending end. Four different types of transmission line faults such as a line to ground fault, double line fault, double line to ground fault, and three-phase fault have been investigated in the presence of linear load (RLC load).

a. Single Phase to Ground Fault

Figure 6: All phase to ground fault with R-L-C load

Table 2: Peak point current and distance

Type of phase to ground fault	Peak point current(A)	Distance (km)
AG	7	16.8
BG	6	13.2
CG	6	14.4

b. Double Phase to Ground Fault

Figure 7: All Double phase to ground fault with R-L Table

Table 3: Peak point current and distance

Type of Double phase to ground fault	Peak point current(A)	Distance (km)
ABG	10,4	24.8
ACG	10,4.5	24.2
BCG	8,7	21.4

c. Double phase to phase fault

Figure 8: All double phase to phase fault with R-L-C load

Table 4: Peak point current and distance

Type of phase to phase fault	Peak point current(A)	Distance (km)
AB	8.3	19.8
AC	5.8	15.2
BC	7	14.1

d. Three phase to phase fault with R-L-C load

Figure 9: abc three phase to phase fault with R-L-C load

Table 5: Peak point current and distance

Type of three phase to phase fault	Peak point current(A)	Distance (km)
ABC	13,12.5,11	26.456

IX. CONCLUSION

Detection and location of faults are very important in the power system as they are the basic of protection of the power system. If detection and location of faults are not accurate the protective devices cannot trip properly and required operation cannot be done, which may leads to damage of the large equipments. In this paper at first, a new method to analyze power distribution system transient signals based MATLAB version 17a is proposed by using WT technique. This method offers important advantages over other methods such as FFT and STFT due to good time and frequency localization characteristics. Analysis results presented clearly show that particular wavelet components can be used as the features to locate the fault in underground cables in distribution system.

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